

Angiotensin receptor-neprilysin inhibition and improved ventricular-arterial coupling in heart failure with reduced ejection fraction

Tina Stegmann MD^a, Luisa Parentin^a, Stephan H. Schirmer MD PhD^b, Philipp Lavall^c
Andreas Hagendorff MD^a, Ulrich Laufs MD^a, Daniel Lavall MD^a

SUPPLEMENT MATERIAL

- Online Figure S1** Representative echocardiographic images
- Online Figure S2** Doses of S/V at the study visits
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- Online Table S1.** Heart failure medication at baseline and 6 months
- Online Table S2.** Quantitative parameters of mitral regurgitation.
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- Online Table S5.** Primary outcomes, secondary echocardiographic and clinical parameters for the subgroup of patients with first diagnosis of heart failure (n=59) vs. pre-existing heart failure diagnosis (n=42).
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- Online Table S7.** Primary outcomes, secondary echocardiographic and clinical parameters for the subgroup of patients with SGLT2i (n=29) vs. patients without (n=73) at baseline.
- Online Table S8.** ANOVA statistical analysis for subgroup analysis.

Supplement Figure Legend

Figure S1

Representative echocardiography images for the measurement of the key parameters for pressure-volume loop construction: left ventricular end-diastolic volume (LVEDV), left ventricular end-systolic volume (LVESV), E and e' velocity in a patient with ischemic (ICM) and an a patient with nonischemic cardiomyopathy (NICM).

Figure S2

Proportions of patients on different doses of S/V at baseline, after 3 months and 6 months.

Supplemental Tables

Table S1. Heart failure medication at baseline and at 6 months

	Baseline	6 Months	p-value
Beta blockers	100 (98.0)	100 (98.0)	1.000
1-49% of target dose	31 (30.4)	28 (27.5)	
50-99% of target dose	39 (38.2)	40 (39.2)	
100% of target dose	30 (29.4)	32 (31.4)	
Mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists	87 (85.3)	76 (74.5)	0.035
25-50% of target dose	81 (79.4)	70 (68.6)	
100% of target dose	6 (5.9)	6 (5.9)	
SGLT2 inhibitors	29 (28.4)	40 (39.2)	0.003
Loop diuretics	71 (69.6)	59 (57.8)	0.017
Torsemide equivalents, mg	20 (0;20)	10 (0;20)	0.075
Ivabradine	2 (2.0)	6 (5.9)	0.125
Antiarrhythmic drugs	6 (5.9)	9 (8.8)	0.250

SGLT2i = Sodium glucose cotransporter type 2 inhibitor. 20mg furosemide were considered as equivalent to torsemide 10mg.
Data are given in numbers (percent) or median with 25% and 75% confidence intervals.

Table S2. Quantitative parameters of mitral regurgitation.

	Baseline	6 Months	p-value
Regurgitant volume (mL)	17 (10;24)	10 (7;17)	0.013
Regurgitant fraction (%)	27 (16;37)	17 (11;21)	<0.001
Effective regurgitant orifice area (cm ²) PISA	0.2 (0.1;0.2)	0.1 (0.1;0.2)	0.296
Regurgitant volume (mL) PISA	50 (20;32)	21 (16;36)	0.834

Continuous data are presented by median (25th and 75th quantiles). We measured the regurgitant volume as the difference between total stroke volume minus forward stroke volume. This method also refers to the regurgitant fraction. Given are the median values only from patients who had mitral regurgitation.
PISA = proximal isovelocity orifice area.

Table S3. Primary outcomes, secondary echocardiographic and clinical parameters for men (n=71) versus women (n=31).

	Baseline			6 Months			Change from Baseline to 6 Months*		
	Male (n=71)	Female (n=31)	p- value	Male (n=71)	Female (n=31)	p- value	Male (n=71)	Female (n=31)	p- value†
Primary Endpoints									
Ees (mmHg/ml)	0.62 (0.45;0.84)	0.76 (0.46;1.11)	0.078	0.75 (0.52;1.00)	0.90 (0.59;1.37)	0.130	0.08 (-0.08;0.26)	0.10 (-0.11;0.37)	0.763
Ea (mmHg/ml)	1.67 (1.38;1.89)	2.22 (2.72;2.72)	<0.001	1.51 (1.28;1.82)	1.92 (1.48;2.27)	0.003	-0.08 (-0.44;0.25)	-0.40 (-0.73;0.08)	0.018
Ea/Ees	2.45 (1.97;1.89)	2.71 (1.67;4.72)	0.697	1.93 (1.51;2.63)	1.81 (1.36;3.07)	0.777	-0.37 (-1.60;0.23)	-0.57 (-1.74;-0.04)	0.460
Secondary echocardiographic and clinical parameters									
LVEDVi (ml/m ²)	110 (99;128)	95 (75;113)	0.002	86 (69;107)	79 (69;95)	0.310	-22.7 (-36.7;-8.7)	-16.3 (-31.8;3.0)	0.061
LVESVi (ml/m ²)	75 (65;95)	65 (49;84)	0.012	51 (34;64)	44 (34;61)	0.369	-21.6 (-38.6;-12.5)	-16.7 (-36.0;-5.6)	0.127
LVEF (%)	32 (27;36)	35 (25;38)	0.301	42 (36;47)	44 (35;51)	0.494	10.0 (4.0;16.0)	10.0 (4.0;18.0)	0.991
LVEDP (mmHg)	19.5 (18.2;21.5)	20.0 (18.2;24.4)	0.327	17.3 (16.2;19.1)	19.1 (18.1;21.5)	<0.001	-2.1 (-3.6;-0.1)	-0.6 (-3.9;1.4)	0.079
NT-proBNP (pg/ml)	1602 (787;4325)	3116 (1043;7298)	0.129	663 (229;1215)	1074(381;3083)	0.016	-657 (-3387;-225)	-1040 (-3862;-214)	0.504
6-MWD (m)	386 (±132)	340 (±105)	0.104	439 (±122)	386 (±117)	0.057	45.8 (±93.0)	43.8 (±69.8)	0.924

Continuous data are presented by mean (±SD) or median (25% and 75% quantiles) as appropriate.

*Presented are the median or mean changes from baseline to six months.

†The p-value represents the comparison of the Δ -value of each parameter resulting from the difference between baseline and six months for men vs. women, respectively.

Ees = end-systolic elastance; Ea = arterial elastance; Ea/Ees = ventricular-arterial coupling ratio, LVEDVi = left ventricular end-diastolic volume index; LVESVi = left ventricular end-systolic volume index; LVEF = left ventricular ejection fraction; LVEDP = left ventricular end-diastolic pressure; NT-proBNP = N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide; 6-MWD = 6-Minute walk distance.

Table S4. Primary outcomes, secondary echocardiographic and clinical parameters for the subgroup of patients with ischemic cardiomyopathy (n=53) vs. non-ischemic cardiomyopathy (n=49).

	Baseline			6 Months			Change from Baseline to 6 Months*		
	ICM (n=53)	NICM (n=49)	p- value	ICM (n=53)	NICM (n=49)	p- value	ICM (n=53)	NICM (n=49)	p- value†
Primary Endpoints									
Ees (mmHg/ml)	0.77 (0.48;0.78)	0.61 (0.42;0.78)	0.033	0.82 (0.66;1.23)	0.74 (0.52;1.07)	0.193	0.012 (-0.15;0.32)	0.13 (0.14;0.35)	0.112
Ea (mmHg/ml)	1.80 (1.53;2.14)	1.80 (1.55;2.18)	0.482	1.61 (1.33;1.91)	1.64 (1.38;2.06)	0.395	-0.09 (-0.47;0.11)	-0.13 (-0.48;0.25)	0.917
Ea/Ees	2.25 (1.57;3.55)	3.21 (2.13;4.37)	0.016	1.81 (1.44;2.47)	2.18 (1.65;3.45)	0.090	-0.21 (-1.34;0.17)	-0.50 (-1.94;0.18)	0.333
Secondary echocardiographic and clinical parameters									
LVEDVi (ml/m ²)	107 (89;127)	107 (95;125)	0.661	87 (70;107)	83 (68;99)	0.229	-17.1 (-29.1;-4.6)	-30.5 (-43.2;-9.8)	0.007
LVESVi (ml/m ²)	71 (56;95)	72 (64;92)	0.423	52 (38;69)	47 (33;62)	0.149	-16.7 (-27.6;-7.7)	-30.1 (-44.2;-13.9)	0.004
LVEF (%)	34 (27;37)	31 (24;37)	0.110	42 (35;47)	43 (38;51)	0.195	8.0 (4.0;11.0)	12.0 (7.5;22.0)	0.007
LVEDP (mmHg)	20 (18;23)	20 (18;22)	0.737	19 (17;21)	17 (16;19)	0.035	-1.0 (-3.1;0.8)	-2.0 (-4.7;-0.8)	0.025
NT-proBNP (pg/ml)	2066 (1113;5611)	1590 (740;4434)	0.424	907 (411;1789)	344 (169;1310)	0.002	-609 (-3628;-147)	-900 (-3428;-237)	0.667
6-MWD (m)	343 (±110)	403 (±134)	0.019	396 (±116)	453 (±123)	0.024	45 (±78)	45 (±95)	0.988

Continuous data are presented by mean (±SD) or median (25% and 75% quantiles) as appropriate.

*Presented are the median or mean changes from baseline to six months.

†The p-value represents the comparison of the Δ -value of each parameter resulting from the difference between baseline and six months for ICM vs. NICM, respectively.

ICM = ischemic cardiomyopathy, NICM = non-ischemic cardiomyopathy; Ees = end-systolic elastance; Ea = arterial elastance; Ea/Ees = ventricular-arterial coupling ratio, LVEDVi = left ventricular end-diastolic volume index; LVESVi = left ventricular end-systolic volume index; LVEF = left ventricular ejection fraction; LVEDP = left ventricular end-diastolic pressure; NT-proBNP = N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide; 6-MWD = 6-Minute walk distance.

Table S5. Primary outcomes, secondary echocardiographic and clinical parameters for the subgroup of patients with first diagnosis of heart failure (n=59) vs. pre-existing heart failure diagnosis (n=42).

	Baseline			6 Months			Change from Baseline to 6 Months*		
	New HF (n=59)	Previous HF (n=42)	p-value	New HF (n=59)	Previous HF (n=42)	p-value	New HF (n=59)	Previous HF (n=42)	p-value†
Primary Endpoints									
Ees (mmHg/ml)	0.66 (0.45;0.92)	0.68 (0.47;0.95)	0.572	0.78 (0.61;1.18)	0.78 (0.52;0.99)	0.290	0.14 (-0.06;0.38)	0.04 (-0.11;0.17)	0.055
Ea (mmHg/ml)	1.76 (1.51;2.25)	1.74 (1.46;2.12)	0.519	1.64 (1.31;1.99)	1.59 (1.42;1.95)	0.812	-0.14 (-0.49;0.21)	-0.08 (-0.41;0.27)	0.469
Ea/Ees	2.61 (1.84;4.24)	2.46 (1.97;3.81)	0.432	1.81 (1.37;2.63)	2.03 (1.62;3.06)	0.219	-0.53 (-2.52;-0.06)	-0.17 (-1.34;0.22)	0.071
Secondary echocardiographic and clinical parameters									
LVEDVi (ml/m ²)	103 (90;122)	109 (97;127)	0.241	78 (67;96)	91 (73;107)	0.021	-23.7 (-39.0;-6.3)	-19.6 (-29.8;-7.6)	0.241
LVESVi (ml/m ²)	71 (57;95)	75 (66;92)	0.401	43 (32;54)	58 (43;69)	0.002	-27.5 (-42.1;-12.5)	-18.0 (-30.3;-9.3)	0.055
LVEF (%)	31 (26;37)	33 (27;36)	0.544	45 (38;51)	39 (34;43)	0.002	12.0 (8.0;21.0)	7.0 (2.0;10.0)	<0.001
LVEDP (mmHg)	20 (19;23)	19 (18;22)	0.318	17 (16;19)	19 (17;21)	0.025	-2.5 (-4.6;-0.4)	-0.4 (-2.6;0.6)	0.011
NT-proBNP (pg/ml)	2233 (1043;5904)	1388 (547;4257)	0.093	683 (216;1881)	773 (349;1494)	0.521	-949 (-3902;-418)	-488 (-2941;-138)	0.079
6-MWD (m)	356 (±104)	388 (±149)	0.230	411 (±128)	437 (±115)	0.329	47 (±93)	44 (±78)	0.847

Continuous data are presented by mean (±SD) or median (25% and 75% quantile) as appropriate.

*Presented are the median or mean changes from baseline to six months.

†The p-value represents the comparison of the Δ -value of each parameter resulting from the difference between baseline and six months for new diagnosed HF vs. pre-existing HF, respectively.

HF = heart failure; Ees = end-systolic elastance; Ea = arterial elastance; Ea/Ees = ventricular-arterial coupling ratio, LVEDVi = left ventricular end-diastolic volume index; LVESVi = left ventricular end-systolic volume index; LVEF = left ventricular ejection fraction; LVEDP = left ventricular end-diastolic pressure; NT-proBNP = N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide; 6-MWD = 6-Minute walk distance.

Table S6. Primary outcomes, secondary echocardiographic and clinical parameters for the subgroup of patients with previous acute decompensated heart failure (n=57) at baseline vs. patients with chronic compensated heart failure (n=45).

	Baseline			6 Months			Change from Baseline to 6 Months*		
	Decompensated HF (n=57)	Compensated HF (n=45)	p-value	Decompensated HF (n=57)	Compensated HF (n=45)	p-value	Decompensated HF (n=57)	Compensated HF (n=45)	p-value†
Primary Endpoints									
Ees (mmHg/ml)	0.61 (0.45;0.97)	0.74 (0.44;0.94)	0.606	0.84 (0.63;1.18)	0.74 (0.54;1.04)	0.189	0.14 (-0.03;0.40)	0.05 (-0.15;0.17)	0.017
Ea (mmHg/ml)	1.83 (1.55;2.23)	1.67 (1.44;1.90)	0.127	1.62 (1.29;1.98)	1.59 (1.38;1.94)	0.906	-0.20 (-0.49;0.22)	-0.07 (-0.39;0.20)	0.413
Ea/Ees	3.20 (1.89;4.09)	2.36 (1.84;4.14)	0.383	1.81 (1.41;2.57)	2.13 (1.55;3.08)	0.296	-0.53 (-1.70;0.10)	-0.08 (-0.97;0.35)	0.078
Secondary echocardiographic and clinical parameters									
LVEDVi (ml/m ²)	104 (92;127)	111 (93;125)	0.606	83 (66;100)	87 (71;107)	0.279	-23.7 (-38.3;-6.4)	-21.0 (-31.0;-6.0)	0.320
LVESVi (ml/m ²)	71 (62;93)	71 (58;94)	0.997	47 (33;64)	53 (39;64)	0.211	-24.1 (-41.0;-11.6)	-18.2 (-31.0;-8.1)	0.183
LVEF (%)	32 (26;35)	34 (27;37.5)	0.149	44 (36;50)	41 (36;46)	0.285	10.0 (6.0;21.5)	9.0 (3.5;12.5)	0.067
LVEDP (mmHg)	20 (19;23)	19 (17;21)	0.209	18 (16;20)	19 (17;20)	0.185	-2.2 (-4.5;-0.4)	-0.9 (-2.7;0.8)	0.026
NT-proBNP (pg/ml)	2725 (1287;6126)	1123 (479;2552)	<0.001	868 (372;1945)	381 (234;1110)	0.037	-2418 (-5044;-428)	-332 (-995;-125)	<0.001
6-MWD (m)	331 (±101)	416 (±135)	<0.001	384 (±113)	470 (±117)	<0.001	48.6 (±87.5)	41.3 (±85.1)	0.696

Continuous data are presented by mean (±SD) or median (25% and 75% quantile) as appropriate.

*Presented are the median or mean changes from baseline to six months.

†The p-value represents the comparison of the Δ-value of each parameter resulting from the difference between baseline and six months for previous decompensated HF vs. chronic compensated HF, respectively.

HF = heart failure; Ees = end-systolic elastance; Ea = arterial elastance; Ea/Ees = ventricular-arterial coupling ratio, LVEDVi = left ventricular end-diastolic volume index; LVESVi = left ventricular end-systolic volume index; LVEF = left ventricular ejection fraction; LVEDP = left ventricular end-diastolic pressure; NT-proBNP = N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide; 6-MWD = 6-Minute walk distance.

Table S7. Primary outcomes, secondary echocardiographic and clinical parameters for the subgroup of patients with SGLT2i at baseline (n=29) vs. patients without SGLT2i as concomitant treatment (n=73).

	Baseline			6 Months			Change from Baseline to 6 Months*		
	SGLT2i n=29	No SGLT2i n=73	p-value	SGLT2i n=29	No SGLT2i n=73	p-value	SGLT2i n=29	No SGLT2i n=73	p-value [†]
Primary Endpoints									
Ees (mmHg/ml)	0.75 (0.44;1.01)	0.62 (0.45;0.91)	0.375	0.90 (0.64;1.16)	0.75 (0.53;1.08)	0.220	0.08 (-0.11;0.36)	0.10 (-0.08;0.30)	0.914
Ea (mmHg/ml)	1.67 (1.48;2.11)	1.78 (1.47;2.19)	0.454	1.62 (1.34;1.95)	1.59 (1.36;1.98)	0.879	-0.13 (-0.41;0.19)	-0.11 (-0.49;0.22)	0.753
Ea/Ees	2.12 (1.56;3.85)	2.71 (1.97;4.16)	0.211	1.83 (1.42;2.36)	2.13 (1.49;2.90)	0.255	-0.24 (-1.38;0.26)	-0.50 (-1.78;0.14)	0.469
Secondary echocardiographic and clinical parameters									
LVEDVi (ml/m ²)	107 (91;130)	106 (93;123)	0.920	86 (65;95)	85 (69;107)	0.451	-24.3 (-40.3;-8.5)	-21.7 (-34.3;-4.6)	0.267
LVESVi (ml/m ²)	71 (56;95)	72 (62;92)	0.730	49 (32;60)	50 (35;69)	0.371	-24.1 (-40.7;-11.7)	-19.8 (-36.7;-9.1)	0.294
LVEF (%)	33 (28;37)	32 (26;37)	0.433	43 (38;49)	42 (35;49)	0.478	10.0 (7.5;14.5)	9.0 (4.0;17.5)	0.659
LVEDP (mmHg)	20 (18;22)	20 (18;23)	0.950	18 (17;21)	18 (16;20)	0.302	-1.1 (-2.5;0.6)	-1.9 (-4.1;0.4)	0.382
NT-proBNP (pg/ml)	1333 (496;3668)	2066 (975;5611)	0.097	392 (220;1005)	813 (325;1945)	0.072	-609 (-2670;-216)	-892 (-3701;-221)	0.658
6-MWD (m)	350 (±107)	380 (±132)	0.285	402 (±117)	431 (±124)	0.312	32.8 (±65.5)	50.6 (±93.5)	0.382

Continuous data are presented by mean (±SD) or median (25% and 75% quantiles) as appropriate.

*Presented are the median or mean changes from baseline to six months.

[†]The p-value represents the comparison of the Δ -value of each parameter resulting from the difference between baseline and six months for patients with SGLT2i at baseline vs. no SGLT2i at baseline, respectively.

SGLT2i = sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors; Ees = end-systolic elastance; Ea = arterial elastance; Ea/Ees = ventricular-arterial coupling ratio, LVEDVi = left ventricular end-diastolic volume index; LVESVi = left ventricular end-systolic volume index; LVEF = left ventricular ejection fraction; LVEDP = left ventricular end-diastolic pressure; NT-proBNP = N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide; 6-MWD = 6-Minute walk distance.

Table S8. ANOVA statistical analysis for subgroup comparisons.

Subgroup	Parameter	p for time effect	p for interaction
Male vs. Female	Ees	0,002	0,760
	Ea	<0,001	0,009
	Ea/Ees	0,001	0,550
Ischemic vs. Non-ischemic HF	Ees	<0,001	0,466
	Ea	0,013	0,618
	Ea/Ees	0,001	0,678
Previous HF vs. New HF	Ees	<0,001	0,027
	Ea	0,022	0,535
	Ea/Ees	0,003	0,124
Compensated vs. Decompensated HF	Ees	<0,001	0,017
	Ea	0,014	0,81
	Ea/Ees	0,002	0,313
SGLT2i vs. No SGLT2i	Ees	0,001	0,909
	Ea	0,041	0,270
	Ea/Ees	0,003	0,889

HF, heart failure; *SGLT2i*, sodium glucose cotransporter type 2 inhibitor.